

Density and viscosity study of binary mixtures of eucalyptol with methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 2-methylpropan-1-ol at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

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Abstract : Density and viscosity of the binary liquid mixtures of eucalyptol with methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 2-methylpropan-1-ol have been measured at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. From density and viscosity data, the values of excess molar volume (V_m^E), the excess viscosity (η^E) and the excess Gibb's free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) have been determined. The computed results have been fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation. Further, the density and viscosity data have been theoretically analysed for the validity of several viscosity models. The main thrust of the study is to correlate the excess properties and the relevant interaction parameters with the nature of molecular interactions between the mixing components. Deviations from ideal behavior are discussed from the point of view of molecular interactions present between the unlike molecules. The strength of interaction is related to alkyl chain length of alcohols. The results are discussed in terms of the interaction parameters obtained from Grunberg-Nissan, Tamura-Kurata and Hind viscosity models and excess properties.

Keywords : Eucalyptol, viscosity, binary mixture, density.

Introduction

In this paper we report experimental data of densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of binary mixtures of eucalyptol with methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 2-methylpropan-1-ol at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K and excess properties like V_m^E , η^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$. With the purpose to provide new information about these mixtures and to give a qualitative interpretation in terms of molecular interactions of Grunberg-Nissan, Tamura-Kurata and Hind viscosity models are studied.

Results and discussion

The excess molar volume (V_m^E) of binary liquid mixtures was evaluated using the following equation,

$$V_m^E = ((X_1M_1 + X_2M_2)/\rho_{12}) - (X_1M_1/\rho_1) - (X_2M_2/\rho_2) \quad (1)$$

where, X_1 and X_2 are the mole fractions of component 1 and component 2, respectively. M_1 and M_2 are molar masses of component 1 and component 2, respectively. ρ_{12} is densities of the binary liquid mixture, ρ_1 and ρ_2 are densities of component 1 and component 2, respectively.

From Table 1 and Fig. 1, the values of V_m^E are negative for eucalyptol + methanol, + ethanol mixtures and are positive for eucalyptol + 1-propanol, + 1-butanol, + 2-methylpropan-1-ol mixtures over the whole composition range at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. With the rise of temperature, the magnitude of positive or negative V_m^E values have increased for all the five binary mixtures. The increase in the alkyl chain length (methanol to butanol and 2-methylpropan-1-ol) has a positive effect on V_m^E vs X_1 profiles for five binary mixtures at three temperatures.

The minima occur between 0.40 and 0.45 mole fraction of eucalyptol + methanol, + ethanol mixtures and the maxima occur between 0.60 and 0.80 mole fraction of eucalyptol + 1-propanol, + 1-butanol, + 2-methylpropan-1-ol mixtures at three temperatures.

Several effects may contribute to the value of V_m^E and three different effects which may be considered as being important : (a) break up of hydrogen bonding in alcohol and dipolar interaction in eucalyptol and alcohols, (b) interstitial accommodation of one component into the other and (c) the possible hydrogen bond interaction be-

Fig. 1. Excess molar volume (V_m^E), excess viscosity (η^E) and excess Gibb's free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) with mole fraction for eucalyptol (X_1) + methanol (X_2) (Δ), eucalyptol (X_1) + ethanol (X_2) (∇), eucalyptol (X_1) + 1-propanol (X_2) (\square), eucalyptol (X_1) + 1-butanol (X_2) (\bullet), eucalyptol (X_1) + 2-methylpropan-1-ol (X_2) (\odot) at 303.15 K

tween unlike molecules. The actual volume change would, therefore, depend on the relative strength of these three

opposing effects. The effect of interaction between eucalyptol + alcohols becomes less intense as alkyl group of alcohols increase leading to increase in V_m^E value and they fall in following order : eucalyptol + methanol < ethanol < 1-propanol < 1-butanol < 2-methylpropan-1-ol.

The increase in V_m^E values with increase in temperature and chain length suggests for declustering of alcohols at higher temperatures¹ and weaker dipole-dipole interaction due to decreased polarizabilities². The negative V_m^E values for eucalyptol + methanol and ethanol indicate the predominance of structure making effect while positive V_m^E for other selected alcohols explains for dominances of dispersion forces in higher alcohols due to declustering.

The excess viscosity (η^E) were calculated from the following equation,

$$\eta^E = \eta_{12} - (X_1\eta_1 + X_2\eta_2) \quad (2)$$

where, η_1 , η_2 and η_{12} are dynamic viscosities of component 1, component 2 and binary liquid mixture, respectively. A perusal of Table 1 and Fig. 1 show that the values of η^E are negative over the whole composition range for eucalyptol + methanol, + ethanol, + 1-propanol mixtures and are little negative and little positive values over the whole composition range for eucalyptol + 1-butanol, + 2-methylpropan-1-ol mixtures at all three temperatures. With rise of temperature, the η^E values has increased for all five binary mixtures.

Negative η^E throughout the whole range of composition for methanol and ethanol binary mixtures indicates for dispersion and dipolar interactions amongst the molecule⁵ due to formation of smaller units of alcohols during mixing. Small negative or positive η^E values for other selected alcohols may be due to charge transfer and H-bonding interaction between unlike molecules leading to formation of complex species.

The algebraic values of η^E for all molecules of eucalyptol + alcohol fall in the order : eucalyptol + methanol < ethanol < 1-propanol < 1-butanol.

The order again suggests that H-bonding between unlike molecules decreases with increase in chain length of alcohols as observed earlier for 2-chloroethanol + alcohols (methanol to butanol)³.

Table 1. Mole fraction (X_1), density (ρ), viscosity (η), excess molar volume (V_m^E), excess viscosity (η^E) and excess Gibb's free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) for eucalyptol + methanol binary mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

X_1	ρ (kg dm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	V_m^E (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	η^E (mPa.s)	$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)
303.15 K					
0.0000	0.7819	0.5140	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0250	0.7950	0.5305	-0.0188	-0.0291	1.2105
0.0740	0.8158	0.5627	-0.0474	-0.0863	200.1013
0.1570	0.8411	0.6343	-0.0815	-0.1645	371.5570
0.2880	0.8667	0.7818	-0.1071	-0.2541	541.9910
0.4290	0.8841	0.9776	-0.1134	-0.3135	593.0162
0.6000	0.8979	1.2654	-0.1063	-0.3352	502.4984
0.7350	0.9056	1.5472	-0.0901	-0.2973	360.8143
0.8720	0.9115	1.9037	-0.0584	-0.1894	181.4291
0.9640	0.9147	2.1966	-0.0202	-0.0632	52.7761
1.0000	0.9158	2.3245	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
308.15 K					
0.0000	0.7777	0.4812	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0250	0.7908	0.4964	-0.0184	-0.0263	82.7252
0.0740	0.8115	0.5238	-0.0462	-0.0775	199.3343
0.1570	0.8368	0.5856	-0.0773	-0.1504	358.9532
0.2880	0.8623	0.7152	-0.0963	-0.2339	517.7472
0.4290	0.8796	0.8894	-0.0962	-0.2886	567.4024
0.6000	0.8935	1.1523	-0.0871	-0.3042	490.4550
0.7350	0.9012	1.4091	-0.0749	-0.2673	356.6476
0.8720	0.9072	1.7311	-0.0506	-0.1672	182.8982
0.9640	0.9104	1.9933	-0.0182	-0.0551	53.6753
1.0000	0.9115	2.1062	0.0000	0.0000	0.0052
313.15 K					
0.0000	0.7723	0.4502	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0250	0.7853	0.4623	-0.0124	-0.0242	75.7960
0.0740	0.8061	0.4864	-0.0322	-0.0704	190.2421
0.1570	0.8314	0.5376	-0.0563	-0.1375	334.1554
0.2880	0.8573	0.6479	-0.0754	-0.2153	475.4675
0.4290	0.8747	0.8003	-0.0812	-0.2652	523.4343
0.6000	0.8889	1.0354	-0.0773	-0.2751	461.5576
0.7350	0.8967	1.2656	-0.0654	-0.2376	343.3758
0.8720	0.9028	1.5542	-0.0412	-0.1462	181.0859
0.9640	0.9064	1.7844	-0.0143	-0.0479	52.8732
1.0000	0.9072	1.8845	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

The excess Gibb's free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) for the binary liquid mixture was computed from the following equation,

$$\Delta G^{\#E} = RT \{ \ln(\eta V) - X_1 \ln(\eta_1 V_1) - X_2 \ln(\eta_2 V_2) \} \quad (3)$$

where V_1 , V_2 and V are the molar volumes of the component 1, component 2 and mixture, respectively. R and T have their usual meaning.

It can be observed from the Table 1 and Fig. 1 that the $\Delta G^{\#E}$ values are both positive and negative for all five binary mixtures. The $\Delta G^{\#E}$ values decrease with increase of temperature for eucalyptol + methanol mixture and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ values increase with increase of temperature for eucalyptol + ethanol, + 1-propanol, + 1-butanol and +2-methylpropan-1-ol mixtures. The curves of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ vs X_1 are systematic (with one maxima) for eucalyptol + methanol, + ethanol, + 1-butanol mixtures at three temperatures and the curves are not systematic (with maxima and minima) for eucalyptol + 1-propanol, + 2-methylpropan-1-ol mixtures at three temperatures.

It has been reported⁴⁻⁶ that $\Delta G^{\#E}$ parameter can be considered as a reliable criteria to detect or exclude the presence of interactions between unlike molecules. According to these authors, the magnitude of positive values is an equivalent indicative of strength of possible specific interactions and magnitude of negative values is indicative of weak interactions. $\Delta G^{\#E}$ values for the systems under study suggest the following order but in case of butanol and 2-methyl 1-propanol no systematic order is found.

Eucalyptol + methanol < ethanol < 1-propanol

The above order is in accordance with viscosity results of these molecules.

The results of V_m^E , η^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ are fitted in the Redlich-Kister⁷ equation,

$$Y^E = X_1(1 - X_1) \sum_{i=0}^n a_i(2X_1 - 1)^i \quad (4)$$

where, Y^E refers to V_m^E (dm³ mol⁻¹) or η^E (mPa.s) or $\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol⁻¹). X_1 is the mole fraction of the first component in the binary mixture and a_i are the estimated coefficients of binary functions. In each case, the optimum number of coefficients a_i was ascertained from an examination of the variation of the standard deviation (σ). The second order form of eq. (5) gives the minimum

standard deviation in Y^E . The standard deviation (σ) was calculated using following equation,

$$\sigma = \{\Sigma (Y_{\text{exp}}^E - Y_{\text{fit}}^E)^2 / (n - p)\}^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where, Y_{exp}^E is the experimentally derived excess (or deviation) function. Y_{fit}^E is the fitted or calculated value of the respective functions. 'n' is the number of coefficients used for fitting the data, 'p' is the number of experimental points and a_i is the coefficient obtained by fitting equation. The values adopted for the coefficients, a_i and standard deviation, σ associated with the use of eqs. (4) and (5) are recorded in Table 2.

Table 2. Estimated coefficients of mixing functions for eucalyptol + methanol binary mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

Functions	a_0	a_1	a_2	σ
303.15 K				
V_m^E (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.4462	0.0794	-0.2382	0.0002
η^E (mPa.s)	-1.3272	-0.3151	-0.2271	0.0016
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	2243.6436	-875.6650	100.5723	7.3149
308.15 K				
V_m^E (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.3721	0.1072	-0.2901	0.0002
η^E (mPa.s)	-1.2173	-0.2564	-0.1493	0.0016
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	2145.9800	-848.2710	251.1820	10.0505
313.15 K				
V_m^E (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.3230	0.0452	-0.1421	0.0002
η^E (mPa.s)	-1.1081	-0.1949	-0.1126	0.0008
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	2003.3136	-734.0759	288.2754	8.9742

Viscosity models and interaction parameters :

Several models (equations) have been put forward from time to time for correlating the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures with those of the liquid components with a view to interpreting the molecular interactions in the liquid mixtures in terms of interaction parameters of the viscosity models.

The following models are used in the present study to account for the molecular interactions and the values obtained are presented in Table 3 :

(i) Grunberg and Nissan⁸ have suggested the following logarithmic relation between the viscosity of the binary liquid mixture and pure components,

$$\ln \eta = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + X_1 X_2 d_{12} \quad (6)$$

where, d_{12} is a constant, proportional to interchange energy.

(ii) Tamura and Kurata⁹ have developed the following equation for the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures,

$$\eta = X_1 \phi_1 \eta_1 + X_2 \phi_2 \eta_2 + 2(X_1 X_2 \phi_1 \phi_2)^{0.5} \cdot T_{12} \quad (7)$$

where, T_{12} is the interaction parameter, which depends on temperature and composition of the mixtures. ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 are the volume fractions of components 1 and 2, respectively.

(iii) Hind *et al.*¹⁰ have suggested the following equation for the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures,

$$\eta = X_1^2 \eta_1 + X_2^2 \eta_2 + 2X_1 X_2 H_{12} \quad (8)$$

where, H_{12} is Hind interaction parameter and is attributed to unlike pair interactions. It can be seen from Table 3 that interaction parameter, d_{12} are negative for eucalyptol + methanol, + ethanol, + 1-propanol mixtures at three temperatures. d_{12} are negative and positive for eucalyptol + 1-butanol and + 2-methylpropan-1-ol mixtures respectively at three temperatures.

Interaction parameter, H_{12} are positive for all five binary mixtures at all temperatures. T_{12} are negative for eucalyptol + methanol, + ethanol, + 1-propanol mixtures and are negative and positive for eucalyptol + 1-butanol and + 2-methylpropan-1-ol mixtures at different temperatures.

H_{12} and T_{12} increase with increase of alkyl chain length in eucalyptol + alcohols implies that dipole-dipole interaction is weaker in higher alcohols. The negative values of d_{12} and T_{12} indicate the dominance of dispersion forces and on the other hand the positive values of d_{12} and T_{12} may be attributed to the presence of strong interactions¹¹.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of analytical grade. Various chemicals like eucalyptol (Aldrich >99% pure) and methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol, 2-methylpropan-1-ol (E. Merck >99.7% pure) were purified by the recommended methods¹².

Binary mixtures were prepared by mixing of different volumes of two liquids in specially designed ground glass air tight ampules and weighed in single pan balance (Mettler Toledo AB 204 electronic balance) to an accuracy of ± 0.0001 g. Preferential evaporation losses of solvent from the mixture were kept to a minimum as evidenced by repeated measurements of physical properties over an interval of 2-3 days during which time no changes in physical properties were observed. The po-

Note

Table 3. Values of interaction parameters H_{12} , d_{12} and T_{12} for eucalyptol + methanol binary mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

X_1	Φ_1	303.15 K			308.15 K			313.15 K		
		H_{12}	d_{12}	T_{12}	H_{12}	d_{12}	T_{12}	H_{12}	d_{12}	T_{12}
0.0000	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.0250	0.1	0.8212	-0.2840	-0.0934	0.7624	-0.2797	-0.0830	0.6732	-0.4082	-0.0771
0.0740	0.2	0.7923	-0.3246	-0.1640	0.7292	-0.3465	-0.1476	0.6582	-0.4137	-0.1333
0.1570	0.3	0.7994	-0.2042	-0.2256	0.7274	-0.2586	-0.2062	0.6504	-0.3451	-0.1881
0.2880	0.4	0.7996	-0.0789	-0.2808	0.7233	-0.1417	-0.2585	0.6422	-0.2341	-0.2376
0.4290	0.5	0.7794	-0.0201	-0.3166	0.7041	-0.0764	-0.2916	0.6260	-0.1572	-0.2676
0.6000	0.6	0.7214	-0.0194	-0.3419	0.6602	-0.0525	-0.3102	0.5926	-0.1092	-0.2811
0.7350	0.7	0.6559	-0.0359	-0.3366	0.6084	-0.0561	-0.3023	0.5569	-0.0918	-0.2693
0.8720	0.8	0.5710	-0.0601	-0.2833	0.5442	-0.0653	-0.2505	0.5132	-0.0803	-0.2184
0.9640	0.9	0.5181	-0.0637	-0.1679	0.5034	-0.0631	-0.1474	0.4750	-0.0806	-0.1289
0.0000	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

ssible error in mole fraction is estimated to be around 0.0001.

Densities accurate to $\pm 0.00001 \text{ kg dm}^{-3}$ were measured by using pycnometer having bulb volume of 10 dm^{-3} and capillary with internal diameter 1×10^3 micrometer for each measurement. The pycnometer was calibrated by using conductivity water (conductivity was $\sim 1 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with 0.99565, 0.99403 and 0.99221 kg dm^{-3} at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K respectively¹³. The pycnometer filled with air bubble free liquids was kept in a transparent walled bath with accuracy of ± 0.01 °C. The temperature accuracy was checked intermittently by means of a calibrated thermometer after 10–15 min of attainment of thermal equilibrium in High Precision Water Bath, Cat No. MSW-274 thermostat.

The kinematic viscosities of both the pure liquids and liquid mixtures were measured at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K at atmospheric pressure with a Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer, having a capillary bore with an internal diameter of about 1×10^3 micrometer and capillary length of 65×10^3 micrometer.

The viscometer was calibrated and two constants A and B of the viscometer were obtained at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K using the equation,

$$v = \eta/\rho = (At - B/t) \quad (9)$$

where, A and B are constants of the viscometer, ρ is the density and t represents the flow time in seconds. The flow time of pure liquids and liquid mixtures are measured using an accurate stop watch with a precision of ± 0.01 s. The reproducibility of viscosity results was found

to be within ± 0.001 mPa.s. Sufficient time was allowed to attain thermal equilibrium in the same water bath and the bath temperature was monitored to ± 0.01 °C with a calibrated thermometer.

Conclusion :

The observed properties and Hind's interaction parameter, H_{12} of mixtures studied support the view that interaction between unlike molecules is predominant. Dispersion forces are operative in mixtures of eucalyptol + methanol, ethanol and propanol, while H-bonding may be the interaction in eucalyptol + butanol and 2-methyl 1-propanol unlike molecules.

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